

Influence of Parenting Styles on Conduct Disorder in Pre-Primary Schools in North West, Nigeria

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Published on 30 Oct 2025</p> <p>Keywords: Authoritarian Parenting Styles Authoritative Parenting Styles Permissive Parenting Styles Conduct Disorder Pre-primary School</p>	<p>This study investigates the influence of family size on conduct disorder among pre-primary school pupils in the North-West region of Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design guided by three research questions and three hypotheses. The research population consisted of public pre-primary school pupils in the North-Western region of Nigeria. The study used a sample size of 378, employing a simple random sampling technique. A structured survey questionnaire with a 4-point rating system was used to collect data. The instruments were validated, and a trial test was conducted to assess the reliability of the instrument. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the study hypotheses at a 0.05 significance level. The findings revealed that all the parenting styles have a significant influence on the conduct disorder exhibited by pre-primary school pupils. It was also established that the majority of parents of pre-primary school pupils in North-western Nigeria employ a permissive style of parenting to nurture their children. To reduce the number of pupils with conduct disorders and alleviate the workload for teachers in classroom settings, it is recommended that workshops and seminars be held to educate parents on the importance of adopting authoritative parenting techniques.</p>

1. Introduction

Conduct disorder is a significant mental health issue in Nigeria; it is usually identified in educational institutions and is typified by improper conduct and other externalising behaviours. Prior studies have indicated that conduct disorder is the fifteenth most common cause of developmental delay in children worldwide (Yockey et al., 2019). Even with present-day intervention options, conduct disorder is still a serious mental health issue because it puts children at higher risk of having a lower quality of life (Yockey et al., 2019). The academic literature showcases several terms employed concurrently, but all of them have similar implications: conduct disorder, behaviour disorder, behaviour problem, disruptive behaviour, abnormal behaviour, oppositional defiant disorder, among others. Thus, conduct disorder is a term that refers to improper actions that hinder children's ability to operate and navigate the learning environment (Samson et al., 2020). It is a behaviour in children that is at variance with the generally accepted values and norms of a given society, such as aggressiveness toward peers or siblings, fighting, telling lies, loitering, absenteeism, and unnecessary crying, among others (Tanko, 2025). Stressing further, it is a behaviour that does not correspond with the conventional values a given society recommends for its group. Conduct disorder manifests differently in individuals from various backgrounds, yet its similarities persist across diverse socio-cultural contexts.

The most prevalent type of conduct disorder among pre-primary pupils in Nigeria is moral disorder. These types of conduct disorders are unacceptable in the classroom and our society and are of significant concern to educators, psychologists, school counsellors, sociologists, and the government (Paul, 2016). Stealing, skipping school, engaging in illegal activities, loitering around, lying, making noise, and fighting are examples of moral disorder (Paul, 2016; Kama, 2015). In addition, conduct disorder within educational institutions has grown out of control and is now affecting every aspect of the educational system like wildfire. The origin of conduct disorder may be linked to family factors (Wanxue, 2019). In support of the above claim, Kendra (2015) posits that several potential causes contribute to these abnormal behavioural patterns, including an unhealthy mindset, inadequate parenting training, poor conduct

conditioning, and the prevalence of flawed models of behaviour, all of which might be a result of parenting styles adopted by parents at home. Parenting styles play a significant role in moulding an individual's personality and behaviours. Parenting styles revolve around monitoring and supervision, which parents might vary in the way they socialise and exercise control over their children. Parenting styles relate to how parents encourage adherence to laws and societal norms, as well as responsiveness, which is correlated with their level of engagement with their offspring (Hosokawa & Katsura, 2018). Samson et al. (2020) stated in their submission that parenting style is a mental concept that denotes the standard approaches parents employ in nurturing their children. Wherever the right parenting style is employed in any family, the home is likely to raise well-organised children; however, the opposite will be the case in situations where this is not actualised. Based on the definitions provided by various researchers so far, it can be inferred that the styles parents use in nurturing children may have a positive or negative impact on their conduct. As parents utilise these different parenting styles in training or nurturing children, their conduct and personality are easily moulded.

Many scholars have recommended various parenting styles; nevertheless, for the sake of this investigation, the authors will only focus on the three (3) most important parenting styles: authoritarian, authoritative, and permissive. Several studies have shown that families with authoritative parents influence conduct disorder. According to Singh and Sihag (2022), authoritative parents have a significant influence on pupils' conduct disorder. Saltali et al. (2018) also found a relationship between authoritative parenting and conduct disorder among students. Gidado and Diffang (2024) equally indicated a significant relationship between family background and conduct disorder of senior secondary school students. Likewise, Soleymani & Rastari (2023) reported a similar result, indicating that authoritative parenting styles have a significant and negative association with conduct disorder. Raja and Parveen (2022) also reveal that authoritative parenting has a significant relationship with conduct disorder in pupils. On the contrary, Mensah and Gyimah (2018) found that authoritative parenting styles have no link with children's conduct disorder.

By contrast, coercion, emotional control, verbal aggression, and corporal discipline are more common among authoritarian parents than among non-authoritarian parents. In view of the above, [Mugenyi and Matagi \(2025\)](#) suggest, in their research, that a strong negative association exists between authoritarian parenting style and pupils' conduct disorder. [Gidado & Anyio \(2025\)](#) also found a significant correlation between authoritarian parenting style and students' aggressive behaviour. Similarly, [Singh and Sihag \(2022\)](#) found that authoritarian parents have a significant influence on conduct disorder exhibited by students. [Raja and Parveen \(2022\)](#) also reveal that authoritarian parenting has a significant relationship with conduct disorder in students. On the contrary, [Masud et al. \(2015\)](#) found no relationship between authoritarian parenting style and conduct disorder in students.

Conversely, permissive parents are strong in warmth, allowing autonomy, and encouraging, but weak in firm control, supervision, logic, and explanation ([Sanvictores & Mendez, 2022](#)). [Samson et al \(2020\)](#) revealed that there is a relationship between parenting style and conduct disorder. [Singh and Sihag \(2022\)](#) also revealed that in India, permissive parenting has no significant impact on conduct disorder. [Hoshidar et al. \(2015\)](#) reveal that parenting practices have a significant impact on children's behavioural disorders. [Kumuyi et al. \(2021\)](#) found that permissive parenting has no significant mean difference in the prevalence of conduct disorder. [Hosokawa and Katsura \(2018\)](#) found no relationship between parenting style and conduct disorder. The literature review also led us to the conclusion that the effects of parenting practices might differ between nations.

Even though research on parental practices and conduct disorder in Nigeria is expanding, little is known about the incidence and contributing causes of conduct disorder in the North West of Nigeria, especially in pre-primary schools. Therefore, the study focuses on pre-primary pupils in the North West of Nigeria to close the knowledge gap in the literature.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The rise in conduct disorder among children has been observed in Africa, possibly as a result of the region's widespread economic suffering and recession. Statistics show that children are acting in more disturbing ways, and conduct disorders have significantly increased recently among children ([Kama, 2015](#)). In Nigeria, the situation is far worse in our schools, where pupils wandering around during class have led to numerous kidnappings and fatalities. This poses a severe threat to the continued existence of education globally, particularly in North-west Nigeria.

Various forms of conduct disorders put a strain on learners and hinder their ability to learn, according to observations. Parents and society are very concerned about the poor performance of pre-primary pupils in North West Nigeria. For a considerable amount of time, teachers and the government have made significant efforts to raise the standard of education in North West Nigeria, but the outcome has remained unchanged. Many studies suggest that this may be due to the rise in conduct disorder among learners; at the same time, others, including the authors, believe that poor parenting practices may be one of the reasons for pupils behaving abnormally. Some of these conduct disorders exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in the study area include lateness, dropping out of school, loneliness, fighting, and anger, among others. In light of the aforementioned, the author takes an interest in examining the influence of parenting style on conduct disorder in pre-primary schools in North-West, Nigeria.

1.2 Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the researcher in the study:

- i. What are the parenting styles among pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria?
- ii. To what extent is conduct disorder exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria?
- iii. What is the influence of parenting styles and conduct disorder among pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria?

1.3 Hypotheses

The null hypothesis was formulated and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

Ho: Parenting styles do not significantly influence conduct disorder exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.

2. Methodology

2.2 Research Design

This study employed a descriptive survey design. It is an approach that collects, analyses, and interprets data from a sample that is thought to be representative of the entire population, enabling the study of a collection of people or things in their natural settings ([Ivase, 2019](#)). "Descriptive survey design" is warranted since it allows for the quick collection of extensive data on a large population, determining and reporting the present situation ([Creswell & Creswell, 2018](#)). As a result, only a sufficient number of population samples have been selected for examination. The approach is considered the most suitable for this study, as it aims to investigate how parental practices influence the conduct disorder of pupils in pre-primary schools in the North-Western states of Nigeria.

2.2 Population of the Study

The study comprised every public 'pre-primary' school in the North-Western states of Nigeria. According to published data, there are 9,382 public pre-primary educational institutions in the North-Western states of Nigeria ([FME, 2023](#)). Thus, the study's population includes every nursery three (3) pupils attending public pre-primary educational institutions in the North-Western states of Nigeria, totalling 184,682 nursery three pupils ([FME, 2023](#)).

2.3 Sampling Size and Sampling Procedure

The study utilised a sample size of 378 nursery three (3) pupils using a 'proportionate random sampling' method. The justification for choosing this figure from this population aligns with [Krejcie and Morgan's \(1970\)](#) assertion that a total population of 232,766 yields a sample size of 384, as shown in the table. The rationale for selecting this number from the population supports [Krejcie and Morgan's \(1970\)](#) claim that a total population of 232,766 results in a sample size of 378. Two (2) pre-primary schools were chosen from every three (3) senatorial zones of the states in North-West, using a 'simple random sampling' procedure, making a total of forty-two (42) pre-primary schools. The reason for selecting a 'simple random sampling' was based on the notion that each participant in the entire population had an equal and distinct chance of inclusion in the sample. Likewise, caregivers from 42 pre-primary schools chosen will be sampled comparably for the study.

2.4 Instrumentation

The instruments used in the study were validated, and their dependability was evaluated through a trial test. Data were collected through a 37-item questionnaire with a four-point rating scale created by the researcher. In addition, to establish the trend of learning outcomes of pre-primary pupils, educational records from the 1st and 2nd terms of the 2024 academic year were gathered and analysed.

2.5 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The instruments used in the study have been validated, and a trial test was undertaken to ensure their dependability. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability test yielded an index score of 0.79. This is consistent with [Mukherjee's \(1995\)](#) assertion that the overall correlation coefficient should have an average value of about 0.70. As a result, the instrument proved dependable and internally reliable for the investigation.

2.6 Data Collection Procedure

After gaining approval from the school headteachers, the inventory was conducted, and participants were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaires. The researchers promptly provided the respondents with the instrument and comprehensive guidance on completing it, which was gathered shortly after they finished.

2.7 Method of Data Analysis

The "Statistical Package for Social Sciences" (SPSS) was used to organise and prepare the data for analysis. The researcher analysed the data using percentages, mean scores, and standard deviations. Additionally, the study hypotheses were tested using "Analysis of Variance" (ANOVA) at a significance threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$.

3. Results

In this section, the researcher presents the answers to the research questions that guided the study.

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Research Question One: What are the parenting styles among pre-primary school pupils in North-West, Nigeria.

Table 1A: Authoritarian Parenting Styles among Pre-primary School Pupils

Authoritarian Parenting Style	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
I use physical punishment as a way of disciplining my child (ren)	1	4	2.59	1.056
I spank when my child (ren) is/are disobedient.	1	4	2.78	.804
I slap my child (ren) when the child misbehaves	1	4	2.62	.797
I yell or shout when my child (ren) misbehaves	1	4	2.36	.920
I scold and criticise to make my child (ren) improve	1	4	2.88	1.027
I use threats as punishment with little or no justification.	1	4	2.02	.954
I scold when my child (ren)'s conduct does not meet our expectations	1	4	2.92	1.123
I punish by taking privileges away from my child (ren) with no explanation	1	4	2.27	.946
I punish by putting the child (ren) off somewhere alone with no explanation	1	4	2.69	1.024
When the child(ren) asked why they must conform, I replied, Because I said so	1	4	2.71	1.068
I influence my children to do things that do not favour their wishes.	1	4	2.73	1.064
Authoritarian PS	1	4	2.48	1.012
Valid N	102			

Source: Research data, 2025

Table 1A shows the authoritarian parenting style among pre-primary school pupils in North-West, Nigeria. The overall sectional means value is 2.48 less than the criteria value of 2.50. This suggests that parents in the study area did not agree with most of the items related to the authoritarian parenting style. This suggests that only a small number of parents exhibit an authoritarian parenting style towards their children. This implies that the authoritarian parenting style is not rampant in the study area, as opined by other studies.

Table 1B: Authoritative Parenting Styles among Pre-primary School Pupils

Authoritative Parenting Style	Min.	Max.	Mean	Std. Dev.
I encourage my child (ren) to talk about their troubles	1	4	2.48	1.039
I am responsive to children's feelings or needs	1	4	2.71	1.175
I give comfort and understanding when my child (ren) is upset.	1	4	2.93	1.119
I give praise when my child (ren) did well	1	4	2.1	1.11
I have warm and intimate times together with my child (ren)	1	4	2.76	0.899
I give my child (ren) reasons why rules should be obeyed	1	4	2.1	0.951
I explain the consequences of the child (ren)'s behaviour	1	4	2.81	0.882
I explain to my child (ren) how I feel about good and bad behaviour	1	4	2.5	1.039
I show respect for my child (ren)'s opinions by encouraging them to express them.	1	4	2.6	1.108
I encourage my child (ren) to express themselves even when disagreeing with me freely	1	4	2.84	1.13
I allow my child (ren) to give input into family rules	1	4	3.02	1.082
I consider my child (ren)'s desires before asking the child (ren) to do something	1	4	2.57	0.926

I take into account children's preferences in making plans for the family	1	4	2.75	0.977
I discuss with my children the dangers related to negative peer influence	1	4	2.67	1.063
Authoritative PS	1	4	2.66	0.923
Valid N	129			

Source: Research data, 2025

Table 1B shows the authoritative parenting styles among pre-primary school pupils in North-West, Nigeria. The overall sectional means values are 2.66, which is greater than the criteria value of 2.50. This suggests that parents in the study area generally agree with most of the items related to authoritative parenting style. This suggests that many parents exhibit an authoritative parenting style towards their children. This implies that authoritative parenting style is rampant in the study area.

Table 1C: Permissive Parenting Styles among Pre-primary School Pupils

Permissive Parenting Style	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
I give my children free rein to do anything they like	1	4	1.52	.666
I give my children freedom to relate to their peers	1	4	1.84	.881
I allow my children to watch any film they like	1	4	1.82	1.014
I always grant my children's desires	1	4	2.87	.813
I do not have time to advise my children on bad conduct	1	4	2.56	.795
I praise and call my children with big names	1	4	2.45	.938
I tolerate my children's inordinate conduct	1	4	2.23	1.000
I give my children free rein to visit peers any time they wish	1	4	2.12	1.078
My children are not afraid because they know I care less about what they do	1	4	2.27	.940
I am in support of everything my children do	1	4	2.60	1.133
I am not interested in the pattern of life my children are living	1	4	2.39	.932
I allow my children to associate with all kinds of peer groups	1	4	2.46	.796
I give my children free rein to do anything they like	1	4	2.43	.965
Permissive PS	1	4	2.76	.976
Valid N	147			

Source: Research data, 2025

Table 1C shows the permissive parenting styles among pre-primary school pupils in North-West, Nigeria. The overall sectional means value of 3.76 is greater than the criterion value of 2.50. This suggests that the majority of parents in the study area agree with most of the items related to a permissive parenting style. This suggests that parents in the study area highly exhibit a permissive parenting style. This implies that authoritative parenting style is rampant in the study area.

Table 2: Parenting Styles among Pre-primary School Pupils

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.865	3	3.288	3.184	0.024
Within Groups	386.188	374	1.033		
Total	396.053	377			

Source: Research data, 2025

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Table 2 shows that a large number (38.9%) of parents employed a permissive style of parenting, 34.1% employed an authoritative style of parenting, and 27% employed an authoritarian parenting style. The findings show that a large number (38.9%) of parents of pre-primary school pupils in North-western Nigeria employed a permissive style of parenting to nurture their children, followed by authoritative (34.1%), and lastly, authoritarian (27%).

Research Question Two: To what extent is conduct disorder exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria?

Table 3: Extent of conduct disorders exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in North-West, Nigeria

S/No.	Types of Conduct Disorder	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Aggressiveness toward peers	2.43	0.945
2	Fighting among pupils	2.47	0.961
3	Loitering during school hours	2.8	0.997
4	Stealing	2.12	0.989
5	Telling lies	2.66	1.028
6	Absenteeism	2.72	0.942
7	Noise making	2.8	1.012
8	Unnecessary crying	2.67	0.963
9	Lateness to school	2.51	1.01
10	Not following simple rules	2.53	0.988
11	Inattentiveness in class activities	2.77	1.008
12	Over-eating	2.65	0.988
13	Temper tantrums	1.92	0.833
14	Low self-esteem	2.56	0.968
15	Difficulty in making friends	2.51	0.862
Disorder Conduct	Sectional Mean/Std. Mean	2.56	0.92

Source: Research data, 2025

Table 3 presents the prevalence of conduct disorder among pre-primary school pupils in North-Western Nigeria. Items 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, and 15 had mean values greater than the criterion value of 2.50. This means that pupils in pre-primary school acknowledged that they are exhibiting these conduct disorders. The table also indicates that the mean values for items 1, 2, and 4 are less than the 2.50 criterion value, showing that pre-primary school pupils rarely exhibit these conduct disorders. The overall sectional means of 2.56 indicate that pupils in the study area exhibit conduct disorders. It is therefore concluded that the pupils' conduct violates the school's rules and moral standards.

3.2 Test of Hypothesis

Ho.: Parenting styles do not significantly influence conduct disorder exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 4: ANOVA Computation of Parenting Style on Conduct Disorder

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.865	3	3.288	3.184	0.024
Within Groups	386.188	374	1.033		
Total	396.053	377			

Source: Research data, 2025

One-way ANOVA was calculated to investigate the influence of parenting style on conduct disorder. The findings in Table 4 show that there was a significant influence of parenting style on conduct disorder of pre-primary school pupils at $p = .000 < 0.05$. Because of this test, the "null hypothesis" was rejected ($F = 3.184$; $p < 0.05$; $df = 3$). This result implies that parenting style has a bearing on conduct disorder exhibited by pre-primary school pupils in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 5: Means of Conduct Disorder Based on Parenting Style

Parenting Style	Conduct Disorder	
	Mean	N
Authoritarian	2.48	102
	Std. Deviation	1.012
Authoritative	2.44	129
	Std. Deviation	0.991
Permissive	2.47	147
	Std. Deviation	1.042

Source: Research data, 2025

Table 5 indicates the mean score of conduct disorder based on parenting style. The authoritarian parenting style has a total mean score of 2.48, the authoritative parenting style has a total mean score of 2.44, and the permissive parenting style has a mean score of 2.47. The authoritarian style of parenting, therefore, has the highest mean, followed by the permissive style, and the authoritative style has the least. This is an indication that authoritarian and permissive parenting styles are the leading variables responsible for conduct disorder among pre-primary school pupils in North-West Nigeria.

4. Discussion of Findings

The research aimed to investigate the influence of parenting styles on conduct disorder of pre-primary school pupils in North-western Nigeria. The study found that the most commonly used parenting style in the research area is permissive parenting (38.9%), followed by authoritative parenting (34.1%), and lastly, authoritarian parenting (27%), as indicated by the mean score. Nevertheless, this finding did not correlate with the claim of [Steinberg et al. \(2022\)](#) and [Chao \(2001\)](#) that African parents are more authoritarian in their techniques of controlling their children than permissive and authoritative. According to [Baumrind \(2013\)](#), [Kim, and Chung \(2003\)](#), authoritative parenting is becoming more widespread in non-Western countries, possibly as a result of exposure to Western culture. According to the current study, parents in the North-Western state are permissive, meaning they are receptive to their children's needs, particularly during the preschool age.

Similarly, the findings revealed that the overall sectional mean for conduct disorder is 2.56, indicating that pupils in the study area exhibit conduct disorders. It is therefore concluded that the pupils' conduct violates the school's rules and moral standards. The findings supported [Paul's \(2016\)](#) and [Kama's \(2015\)](#) argument that abnormal activities in educational institutions include stealing, fighting, fabricating falsehoods, rioting, and examination malpractice, among others. These are regular, damnable behaviours committed by pre-primary school pupils. For example, fighting is a common type of misbehaviour among pupils. The findings were also consistent with [Wisegeek \(2013\)](#), who defined conduct disorder as an activity that does not conform to widely accepted cultural or social standards.

Furthermore, the study's findings showed that all three types of parenting styles have a significant influence on conduct disorder in pre-primary school pupils in North-western Nigeria. The authoritarian style of parenting, therefore, has the highest mean, followed by the permissive style, and the authoritative style has the least. This is an indication that authoritarian and permissive parenting styles are the leading factors responsible for conduct disorder among pre-primary school pupils in North-West Nigeria. This finding agrees with the finding of [Samson et al \(2020\)](#), which revealed that there is a relationship between parenting style and conduct disorder. Additionally, [Hoshiar et al. \(2015\)](#) reveal that parenting practices have a significant impact on children's behavioural disorders. This finding is contrary to the finding of [Hosokawa and Katsura \(2018\)](#), who found no relationship between parenting style and conduct disorder. The literature review also led us to the conclusion that the effects of parenting practices might differ between nations.

5. Conclusion

The following conclusions were derived from the study's findings: analysis of the responses from the pupils' parents revealed that, contrary to expectations, all parenting styles had a significant influence on the conduct disorders of pre-primary school pupils. Parents of pre-primary school pupils

in North-western Nigeria employ a permissive style of parenting to nurture their children, whereas authoritative parenting is more prevalent in Western cultures (Steinberg et al., 2016; Baumrind, 2013). Despite adopting a permissive parenting approach, the study found that parents of pre-primary school children in North-Western Nigeria provide their children with limited liberty. This suggests children do not have the authority to decide for themselves. The study shows that, due to cultural factors, the behavioural and social competence of pre-primary school children in the sample size is not negatively impacted by what is thought to be inappropriate parenting (permissive and authoritarian).

6. Recommendations

The following suggestions have been made in light of the study's findings.

- i. In order to lower the number of pupils with conduct disorders and to lessen the workload for teachers in classroom settings, workshops and seminars should be held to educate parents on the need to adopt authoritative parenting techniques.
- ii. To produce pupils who behave in a pro-social manner, the government should also create a program to educate educators and parents about the adverse effects of permissive and authoritarian child-rearing methods. Thus, an environment that is conducive to successful teaching and learning will be established. The government may do this by mandating that all parents of students attend all PTA meetings that each school hosts.

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